

Self Guided Learning: Machine Learning is for the Birds.

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Prologue

It is rare to have a prologue to an academic manuscript, but this manuscript is unusual. It was written more than 30 years ago. Why it is only now appearing on an archive deserves an explanation.

This is a reconstruction of a manuscript that we [MRD, DDR] wrote in 1993 and submitted to the journal, *Machine Learning*.³ The original manuscript was rejected. The memorable comments of the editor and reviewers were that (1) the premise of the article (self guided, inductive learning)⁴ was deeply flawed and unworthy of publication—after all “we know” that induction fails; and (2) humour should never be used in academic journals—a reference to our title.

History appears to have been on our side. Machine learning algorithms that generate their own learning opportunities took off in the late “noughts” and have become common place in machine learning and AI approaches.

Our approach to self guided, inductive learning was incipient. To a modern reader it would look childish. Nonetheless, the approach is so simple and so easily developed and expanded that it has value for exploring some core issues in self guided, inductive learning: bias, memory, and generalisability being three of them.

At the time we wrote the manuscript, in the early 1990s, we thought it was the first example of self guided, inductive learning within a machine learning paradigm. Areas like active learning and instance-based learning were well into their developmental stages, and reinforcement learning was a recognised and growing area. However, concepts like AdaBoost and more refined notions of (what is now called) “self-supervised learning” were still on the horizon. The specific focus of SeGuL on iteratively learning from self-identified positive cases appears to have been novel.

There are, thus, three reasons for placing this reconstruction of our 30-year old manuscript on a repository.

The first reason is ego. We were there too (even if you missed us)! Once we received the rejection from *Machine Learning*, we ceased working on those ideas and moved on to other things. Our work gathered dust, the manuscript lay around as a partial paper copy (see the associated web resources in the archive) and the ideas never contributed anything to the area—except perhaps as thistledown sown in reviewers’ and editors’ minds. The manuscript does, however, show one thing clearly. Zeitgeist. Research ideas swirl around communities of scientists at particular times. If the ideas arrive too early or they are not embedded within collegiate communities, they will fall

³ The draft manuscript on which we based the reconstruction is available here:

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10572201>

⁴In modern parlance this would probably be referred to as a form of “self-supervised learning”, which came into common use as a term around the mid-2010s.

on fallow ground. But someone else will inevitably think of something like it—because the ideas needed to be thought.

The second reason for archiving the manuscript is that, simple as our approach was, SeGuL provides an easy model for exploring ideas around self guided, inductive learning. We struggled for example with how the data set (which grew and grew over time) could detect changes in the environment. If a learning algorithm has identified that it is short old men who smuggle drugs and that is where it focuses its detection and learning efforts, how will it know to shift its focus when the market shifts and it is now tall young women who are smuggling drugs? To overcome memory being baked in, it is now common to weight the learning by recency and to include random perturbations in the weights which allows for the detection of changes in the environment.

Finally, while SeGuL as we instantiated it was trivial, the fundamentals of the idea so obviously extends into many learning algorithms that the generalisability holds. We had originally started coding SeGuL as an artificial neural net (ANN) in C. Laziness won, however. If we used ordinary least squares regression (a kin to the already defunct perceptron), we could write the entire code in about 30 minutes as a shell script on a single floppy drive PC with an 8086 CPU. Coding and revising the ANN took longer and “learning” in ANNs is a much slower, iterative approach.

Unlike the original manuscript, in this reconstruction we have embedded footnotes to comment on different aspects of the ideas and to note where the 2024 reconstruction of the paper diverges from the original. For example, the Figures are lost, but we know how to reconstruct them. Thus, the Figures will convey the idea correctly but will not be perfect representations of the original Figures. We have also rewritten the code-base in R and made the code available [<https://github.com/dreidpath/SeGuL>].(Reidpath and Diamond, 2024)

Abstract⁵

This manuscript introduces the concept of Self Guided Learning (SeGuL) in the realm of machine learning. We propose a novel approach that allows a machine learning algorithm to develop its own rules for case selection iteratively, thereby engaging in a self-guided, inductive learning process. This methodology stands in contrast to traditional machine learning paradigms, where case selection is predefined by researchers. SeGuL, as explored in this study, employs linear regression as its core algorithm largely for its simplicity. It allowed the exploration of an idea about inductive machine learning without getting caught in an algorithmic trap.

To test the efficacy of the SeGuL approach, our research involves the creation and analysis of four distinct databases, each with 3000 cases,. The uniqueness of SeGuL lies in its iterative process where each new rule for case selection is informed by the outcomes of previous self-selections, allowing for an evolving learning model. The results from our simulations reveal that SeGuL can effectively identify positive cases in data sets without requiring curated data. This study not only challenges conventional machine learning methodologies but also opens new avenues for exploring adaptive, self-guided learning algorithms in various applications.

⁵No abstract was recovered from the draft of the 1993 *Machine Learning* manuscript. This abstract was created from the manuscript by ChatGPT4.

Introduction

To date, machine learning researchers have tended to approach the issue of concept formation and exemplar selection tasks by presenting a pre-selected set of multiattribute cases to a learning algorithm and then examining the success with which the machine has learned the concept. Variations on this general approach include the introduction of noise into the data, incremental learning via genetic algorithms (Davis, 1987), or incremental learning via recursive partitioning algorithms (Crawford, 1989; Utgoff, 1989).⁶ This basic learning paradigm is presented in Figure 1.⁷

Figure 1: An illustration of the standard approach to machine learning. Collect a large database of multi-attribute exemplars with classifications and apply an appropriate learning algorithm to the database (e.g., ANN). Use the derived rule to classify future cases.

⁶We did not have the original references. In reconstructing the references we have identified the same or an equivalent reference by the same author from the period.

⁷The original figures have been lost. We have reconstructed them and embedded them in the text rather than at the end of the manuscript.

The feature of that paradigm [i.e., genetic algorithms, recursive partitioning, etc.]⁸ which is germane to this paper is that the cases submitted to the learning algorithm are selected *a priori* by the researchers, either from some pre-existing database or from a database specially constructed. On the other hand, one learning paradigm which appears not to have been examined previously in the machine learning literature is Self Guided Learning (SeGuL) (Bruner et al., 1956; Reidpath et al., 1993).⁹ SeGuL is iterative, where a learner generates a rule (R_n) for selecting a positive case on iteration $n+1$. The rule is generated on the basis of the cases previously selected by rules $R_1 \dots R_{n-1}$ (see Figure 2). In a SeGuL paradigm the cases which will be submitted to the learner could not be known *a priori*, because it is the learner which selects the new case at each iteration.

Figure 2: An illustration of the standard approach to machine learning. Collect a large database of multi-attribute exemplars with classifications and apply an appropriate learning algorithm to the database (e.g., ANN). Use the derived rule to classify future cases.

In terms of optimum learning this paradigm appears to have little to commend it. The self guided nature of the case selection means that terrible bias could enter the positive case list which is

⁸In line variations from the original manuscript are highlighted in blue text, or noted in a footnote.

⁹The original reference was to "(Bruner et al., 1956; Reidpath and Diamond, 1992)". The Reidpath and Diamond (1992) reference was a working paper that has since been lost. However, the ideas of that working paper were developed and written up for a journal article published in *Chance* (Reidpath et al. 1993). It is used here as an appropriate substitute.

used in the inductive learning (Reidpath et al., 1993).¹⁰ Indeed, Bruner (1980)¹¹ argued that this type of bias was instrumental in preventing humans from obtaining a veridical perception of reality. Notwithstanding these difficulties, there are a number of instances in which humans appear to employ this learning paradigm, and they employ it because their aim is not to obtain a veridical perception of reality, but to select cases which possess a particular attribute. For example, an insurance fraud investigator who must select claims to investigate. The investigator has to screen thousands of insurance claims in order to select the few claims which his limited resources will allow him to investigate (see (Reidpath, 1992)). His job requires him, in every instance, to select claims which he believes constitute a fraud. He selects a claimant to investigate and, on the basis of the results of that investigation, adjusts the “algorithm” by which he selects the next claimant to investigate. He continues this process *ad infinitum*, always keeping in mind that he cannot afford to waste time selecting claimants who are not defrauding the insurance company. Other examples of SeGuL include selecting the best students for admission into a graduate program, selecting the best job applicant for an employment vacancy, and triaging patients in a hospital emergency department.

The aim of this study was to develop a machine implementation of SeGuL. In this instance by employing a simple statistically based learning algorithm — linear regression (Bowerman et al., 1986). Since the demonstrated failure of the perceptron to cope with linearly inseparable logical XOR data-sets (Minsky and Papert, 1969) machine learning theorists have largely ignored linear modeling techniques as an approach to machine learning. This notwithstanding the success of linear models at modeling human judgement in a wide range of tasks (Kahneman et al., 1982).¹² This study could equally have used any other induction algorithm in its stead, since the critical feature of the SeGuL paradigm is the selection of positive cases, and not the resolution of the structure underlying the data.

Method

Outline

The learner was initialised with a rule (R_0), and with a list (L) of randomly selected cases for round 1. Each iteration (i), beginning with $i = 0$, of the learning process comprised the following steps:

¹⁰The Reidpath and Diamond (1992) reference was a working paper that has since been lost, its replaced here by Reidpath et al. (1993) as an appropriate substitute.

¹¹Jerome S. Bruner did not publish a relevant paper in 1980, and we are unable to check the citation against the references to determine the correct citation. However, the problems of induction were widely discussed at the time. Alternative citations could include Bruner (1979) in the chapter on *The Act of Discovery*, Brehmer (1980), Evans (1989), or one could just go back to Hume (1739). Evans has a particularly interesting discussion about the problems with inductive learning and critiques of Wason’s 2, 4, 6 problem (Evans, 2007).

¹²In our draft of the manuscript there was instruction to ourselves to include “(LOTS OF REFERENCES HERE)”. For the purposes of this, we have replaced our instruction with a reference to the classic edited collection of paper on judgement and reasoning by Daniel Kahneman, Paul Slovic, and Amos Tversky. It isn’t the only example available, but it is a solid contemporary reference.

- Step 1. Read the next five available cases from a database.¹³
- Step 2. Use rule R_i to select from the five current cases the **single** case most likely to be a positive case.
- Step 3. Add the selected case to list L **with information about whether it was in fact a positive or negative case.**
- Step 4. Construct a new rule R_{i+1} from list L .
- Step 5. Increment i .

The various parts of the algorithm are discussed in the four successive subsections. These are followed by a subsection describing the actual databases examined in this paper, and another subsection detailing the initial conditions of the algorithm.

Definition of a Case

A case C was defined as a vector of six real valued attributes x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6 and a dichotomous criterion y . The values for each of the six attributes were generated by a pseudo-random number generator. These were normally distributed (mean = 0, Standard Deviation = 1). The criterion could take the value zero or one, where one indicated a positive case.

Definition of a Rule

A rule R for round $i+1$ was defined as a vector of six values, referred to as a -weights, " $a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{i6}$ ", which were used **in the process of case selection in round $i+1$.**

Case Selection by the Rule

Cases were selected according to the following procedure:

1. For each of the five current cases (**in round $i+1$**) calculate:
value = $a_{i1}x_1 + a_{i2}x_2 + \dots + a_{i6}x_6$, where " $a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{i6}$ " represented the rule R_i .
2. Select the case for which value was greatest, and add the case to the list L .¹⁴

¹³We used this approach as a way of managing queues. We had in mind a queue of passengers where a decision needs to be made whether to search them or not (Reidpath et al., 1993). An update version would probably not work in batches. Instead a probability/risk/score would be allocated to an individual case and a decision made there and then about that individual case. Cut-offs could shift according to available resources for managing selected cases.

¹⁴The obvious problem with this approach is that we used ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to model a binary outcome. Logistic regression would have been a theoretically better choice. There were a number of reasons, however, for choosing OLS. First and foremost was convenience. We used Gary Perlman's "|Stat" package for data manipulation and analysis (Perlman and Horan, 1986). Perlman's utilities were originally written for a Unix environment allowing output to be piped from one utility to the next, and it was later ported to MSDOS. |Stat had an OLS utility (regress) but no logistic regression utility.

Construction of Rule R_{i+1}

The rule R_{i+1} was obtained by a linear regression analysis (Perlman, 1986). The case list L was entered for analysis and the output was of the form:

$Y = a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_6x_6$, where a_k represents the weight of attribute x_k , such that the sum of the weighted attributes had the highest linear correlation with the criterion. The vector of a -weights " a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6 " obtained from the regression analysis constituted the new rule R_{i+1} . As a new case was added to L with each iteration of the learner, so the a -weights were revised to give the best linear estimate of the relationship between attributes x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6 and the criterion y .

As was mentioned earlier, a regression analysis was chosen for reasons of convenience. If another induction algorithm such as CART (Breiman, Friedman, Olshen & Stone, 1984) was employed then the nature of the induced relationship could vary; however, the fact that the induced relationship was an estimate of the relationship between attributes and the criterion would not change, and nor would the fact that the estimate affected the selection of subsequent cases.

The Databases

Four databases were constructed for this research. Each data database comprised 3000 cases, where the attribute values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6 for the 3000 cases were identical across the four databases. The correlation between every attribute pair was low (i.e., $r_{xy} < .05$; where $i \neq j$). The databases differed only with respect to the manner in which the criterion was calculated for each case. Table 1 shows the generative rule employed to determine the criterion value, and the percentage of criterion values equal to one.

Table 1: The names of the four databases, the criterion for generating the value, y , in each database, and the percentage of y -values equal to 1 in each database.

Database	Criterion ¹⁵	Percentage of positive cases
EW ₅₀	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 0$ THEN $y=1$ ELSE $y=0$	50
EW ₂₇	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 1.5$ THEN $y=1$ ELSE $y=0$	27
EW ₅	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 2.5$ THEN $y=1$ ELSE $y=0$	5
XOR	IF $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 > 1.5$	32

¹⁵The table's text was minimally altered to avoid any ambiguity between the criterion (e.g., IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 0$ THEN $y=1$, ELSE $y=0$) and the rule, which is later defined as a set of a -weights. There is also an error in the XOR criterion. The cutoff value is recorded as 1.5, in the simulation it was actually 4. That is, the correct criterion is: IF $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 > 4$ XOR $x_4 + x_5 + x_6 > 4$ THEN $y=1$, ELSE $y=0$

XOR $x_4 + x_5 + x_6 > 1.5$ THEN $y=1$
ELSE $y=0$

Initial Conditions

For a linear regression analysis to function it requires a minimum of n linearly independent cases for every n attributes. For this reason the case list L was seeded with 8 cases, rather than the minimum six because in small samples it is often difficult to ensure linear independence. There were essentially three possible choices to be made about the structure of the 8 initial cases:

1. The cases could have properly generated criterion values according to Table 1,
2. The cases could have incorrect criterion values, by allocating the opposite of the value expected according to Table 1.
3. The criterion values could be randomly assigned to each case, or

The advantage of the first approach was that the learner would not commence the simulation with false information. Unfortunately, this would also give the learner an immediate and "unfair" advantage which could make determining the actual learning capacity of the simulation problematic. The second approach, and the one chosen in this study, was essentially to "lie" to the learner about what constituted a positive case. This put the learner at a maximal disadvantage initially, which meant no criticism could be made about "providing the learner with a friendly shove in the right direction" should the learner finally succeed. The third approach lacked either of the advantages of the first or second approach, and was consequently discounted.

The initial rule R_0 for each of the five experiments was calculated by inputting each of the five initial lists L into a regression analysis. The α -weights from these analyses constituted R_0 for each of the five simulations.

Results

There are a number of ways in which the results of the simulations may be presented. They do, however, fall into two basic categories. The first category of results are those which reflect the proportion of positive cases selected by the learner. This category is of primary importance given that positive case selection is the principal aim of SeGuL. The second category is of those results which reflect iterative changes in the selection rule R, through the α -weights. This reflects the less important issue of whether the learner's model of the selected cases reflects the true underlying structure of the complete data-set. The proportion of positive cases will be presented first followed by the changes in the rule.

Proportion of Positive Cases

It should be kept in mind that the primary motivation for exploring the SeGul paradigm was not to examine the facility with which the learner could determine the underlying structure of the data set, rather it was to determine the facility with which the learner could select positive cases. Table 2 shows the percentage of positive cases in each of the data sets, the maximum number of positive cases that an optimal selection procedure could select, and the percentage of positive cases that the four different models actually did select. In no case could the optimal performance ever be expected to be 100%, because for each of the generative models there was always a probability that any one block of five cases would contain all negative cases. For the EW_{27} model, for example, there was a 73% chance that any one case was negative. This meant that in any block of five cases the probability that at least one of the cases would be positive was

$1 - (1 - .27)^5 = 0.79$. In other words an optimal model could select only 79% positive cases.

Table 2: Optimal positive case selection (OSR), the actual positive case selection rate (ASR), and the base rate of positive cases for each of the four learners: the three equal weights models (EW_{50} , EW_{27} , and EW_5), and the logical exclusive or (XOR) model.

Mode	OSR	ASR	Base rate
EW_{50}	97%	95%	50
EW_{27}	79%	78%	27
EW_5	23%	24% ¹⁶	5
XOR	85%	55%	32

Table 2 indicates that the equal weights models performed optimally, with increases above the base-rate from 19% to 51%. Unsurprisingly, the XOR model performed sub-optimally, although it achieved a selection rate of positive cases 23% greater than that expected by chance alone. In view of the better than chance performance, it is worth spending a little time examining reasons why this may have been so.

The XOR generative model used arithmetic sums of attributes, $x_1+x_2+x_3$ and $x_4+x_5+x_6$. In order to moderate the difficulties of illustrating points in six-dimensional space, $x_1+x_2+x_3$ will be referred to by the single new attribute w_1 and $x_4+x_5+x_6$ will be referred to as w_2 . Now consider the two dimensional equivalent XOR generative model employing the attributes w_1 and w_2 (Figure 3).

A positive case in the two dimensional generative model is represented by the shaded portions of the upper-left and lower-right quadrants. The appropriate logical rule for positive case selection would be $w_1 > 1.5 \oplus w_2 > 1.5$. Clearly there is no single line which could separate the positive case

¹⁶This value is an error and should be closer to about 16%—see the supplementary material in Reidpath & Diamond (2024).

quadrants from the negative case quadrants; and herein lies the problem of linear models in coping with xor generative models. However, the purpose of the learner was not to generate a linear classifier which could deal with an XOR generative model, but to select positive cases.

The two dimensional criterion analogous to the six dimensional criterion employed in XOR learner's would be $\langle -.12, .41 \rangle$. The logical rule equivalent of this is "IF w_1 is high AND NOT w_2 is high THEN select case as a positive case". This rule would, in effect, mean that the learner selected cases from the lower right quadrant and exclude the upper left quadrant.

Figure 3: An illustration of the XOR rule where the positive cases are determined by the criterion: $w_1 > 1.5 \oplus w_2 > 1.5$. That is, $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 > 1.5 \oplus x_4 + x_5 + x_6 > 1.5$.

Table 3 shows the distribution of cases selected during the XOR simulation from the four quadrants! w_1 and $w_2 > 1.5$, w_1 and $w_2 < 1.5$, $w_1 > 1.5$ and $w_2 < 1.5$, and $w_1 < 1.5$ and $w_2 > 1.5$. The figures in italics represent the expected frequency of cases selected in each quadrant given only a random selection procedure, and the figures in bold represent the actual frequency of case selection in each quadrant.

Table 3: The distribution of cases selected during the XOR simulation.¹⁷

¹⁷ Table 3 was entirely missing from the draft of the 1993 *Machine Learning* manuscript. This Table 3 is recreated from the data generated in 2024 (Reidpath and Diamond, 2024).

	$w_1 < 1.5$	$w_1 > 1.5$
$w_2 < 1.5$	199	316
	391	93.5
$w_2 > 1.5$	35	58
	93.5	22

It is apparent from the table that the **second** quadrant (a quadrant of positive cases) was over represented by more than a factor of three (3.38). Quadrant three on the other hand (another positive case quadrant) was under represented by a factor of 2.7.¹⁸ Clearly the learner has not achieved the impossible by generating a linear classifier which can deal with an XOR data-sets; instead the [SeGuL] learner has treated the data set as one containing only a single quadrant of positive cases. With each iteration of the learner, the list L of cases reflected the actual data-set less and less well, and a data set containing a single quadrant of positive cases better and better. The optimal selection rate (given equal distribution of positive cases between the two quadrants) that a linear learner could hope to achieve would be 85%;¹⁹ a figure very close to the actual 55% selection rate.

Figures 4(a) to 4(c) show the changes in the values of the rules' α -weights over time for each of the equal weights models (EW₅₀, EW₂₇ and EW₅). It can be seen that the α -weights for each of those models are converging to single values. This is consistent with the learner having induced the actual underlying equal weights relationship between the attributes and the criterion. In the EW₂₇ and the EW₅ models the α -weights had begun to converge by the 20th iteration, and even the EW₅₀ model had begun to converge by the 100th iteration.

Similarly, figure 4(d) shows the changes in the values of the rules' α -weights over time for the XOR model. As can be seen from the graph, half the α -weights are converging to one value, and half the α -weights are converging to another. Further, it is the weights for attributes x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 which converge to one value, and attributes x_4 , x_5 , and x_6 which converge to the other. Table 1 shows that these two groups of attributes formed the two terms in the XOR model (and the composite attributes w_1 and w_2).

It is apparent that the weights for the XOR model had begun to converge toward two values by the 50th iteration.

¹⁸In the draft of the 1993 *Machine Learning* manuscript this figure was 4.8.

¹⁹In the draft of the 1993 *Machine Learning* manuscript this was incorrectly calculated as 56%, making the remainder of the sentence, "a figure very close to the actual 55% selection rate", completely wrong with respect to "closeness".

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore the facility with which a machine learner, employing a SeGul learning paradigm, could select only positive cases from a data-set. The results of this study may be summed up very simply. The machine learner performed surprisingly well. In fact, the selection rate of positive cases by the learner was in three of the four simulations optimal. Those three simulations employed linear generative models, and as such we may be accused of having used a learner (a regression analysis) which was ready made for the task. This, however, would fail to give sufficient weight to the disadvantage that one might assume self guided learning would place on any learning system.

The fourth model, a generative XOR model, is known to be insoluble by a linear classifier. Notwithstanding that fact, the machine learner selected positive cases 55% of the time, when a random strategy could only select positive cases 32% of the time - an increase of 23%. This success seems to derive in part from the fact that the learner is not required to classify cases as positive or negative, but to select positive cases.

Although the explication of the underlying structure of the total data-set was of secondary importance, the learners for the three linear generative models did nonetheless reflect that structure in their rules for selecting positive cases. The learner for the XOR generative model on the other hand reflected a very different underlying data structure in its rules for selecting positive cases. Despite this failure the XOR learner still achieved a considerable success in selecting positive cases.

These results are surprising in virtue of a number of facts. Firstly, It is known that non random sampling strategies can bias a data-set, and such biases could radically affect inferences drawn on the basis of that sample. (Heckman, 1979) Secondly, there is some evidence in the field of human judgement and decision making to suggest that the type of learning paradigm embodied in SeGul would produce a view of reality which was not veridical, and was therefore suboptimal (Brehmer, 1980). Finally, there are a considerable number of philosophical works, particularly in the tradition of the British Empiricists, to suggest that induction generally is an undesirable strategy for selecting positive cases (Hume, 1739), and a self guided learning strategy would be particularly poor.

In spite of this, machine implementations of SeGul clearly perform better than chance at selecting positive cases, and in the event that the underlying data-structure suits the learning algorithm, it may perform optimally. What is particularly interesting about the success of the machine learner in this environment is that it may well out perform the human learner (Dawes and Corrigan, 1974). This has implications for a number of tasks such as screening insurance claims for fraud investigation (Reidpath, 1992), triaging patients in a hospital emergency

department, selecting international passengers for baggage examination by Customs Officers (Reidpath et al., 1993),²⁰ and selecting personnel to fill job vacancies.

Figure 4: Fig.4a..c illustrates the iterative convergence of the models on b-weights that predict positive cases notwithstanding the self-guided nature of the learning. Fig 4.d, the XOR model illustrates the divergence between the two parameter sets making up the XOR. One set of weights sits close to 0, and the other set are positive ensuring the database of positive cases selected from the XOR space are linearly separable.

²⁰As explained earlier Reidpath and Diamond (1992) is a lost working paper. It is replaced here by Reidpath et al. (1993) as an appropriate substitute.

Given the initial success of this research, additional research focusing on self guided learning system, which can perform a task and continue learning on the run, seems warranted. Questions this research team is focusing its efforts on relate to the performance of tree algorithms, and neural networks in SeGul tasks, as well as comparisons of machine learners with actual human performance.

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